

Synthesis of Some Sulfonamide Derivatives

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Manuscript received 22 September 1976, revised 17 March 1977, accepted 11 April 1977

Various 2-(sulfamyl substituted anilino)-4-(substituted phenyl) thiazoles were prepared by the condensation of different 2-chloroacetophenones with few sulfamyl substituted phenyl thioureas. The presence of imino (-NH-) and -SO₂NH₂ groups were confirmed by IR spectra. Some of the type compounds were tested against antibacterial activity and found to be ineffective.

THE antihistaminic and antianaleptic properties of some secondary and tertiary thiazolyl amines¹, the fungicidal activity of some 2-anilino thiazoles² and the antimalarial activity of some anilino thiazoles³ have been reported. The present paper deals with the synthesis of 2-(sulfamyl substituted anilino)-4-(substituted phenyl) thiazoles with view to ascertaining their possible antibacterial activity. They were obtained by the condensation of different substituted 2-chloroacetophenones with sulfamyl substituted phenyl thioureas which incidentally have so far not been reported in the literature. The procedure described by Frank and Smith⁴ was adopted for the preparation of sulfamyl phenyl thioureas which were used as intermediates for the synthesis of 2-anilino thiazole compounds.

The different 2-chloro acetophenones, viz. 2-chloro-, 2,4'-dichloro-, 2-chloro-4'-methyl-, 2-chloro-4'-bromo-, 2-chloro-4'-iodo-, 2-chloro-2'-fluoro-5'-methyl-, were prepared by Friedel-Craft method and were condensed with thiourea. The melting points of 2-amino-4-(substituted phenyl) thiazoles so obtained corresponded with literature values⁵⁻⁷. Similarly melting points of 2,2',5'-trichloro-, 2,3',4'-trichloro-, 2,2'-dichloro-6'-methyl-, 2-chloro-2'-bromo-5'-methyl acetophenones agreed with reported values⁸.

Experimental

1. Synthesis of sulfamyl phenyl thiourea :

A mixture of ammonium thiocyanate (8g., 0.11 mol.) and acetone (50 ml) was placed in the flask. Benzoyl chloride (15g., 0.1 mol) was added through the dropping funnel with stirring. Sulfonamide (17g., 0.1 mol) in acetone (50 ml) was then added in small portions. When the addition was over, the reaction mixture was refluxed for 30 min and cooled. It was poured over 500 ml ice-cooled water. The precipitate was separated by filtration. The precipitate was heated for half an hour with 10% NaOH solution (100 ml) and cooled. The clear solution was neutralised by dil HCl. The precipitate obtained was filtered and washed with 2% NaHCO₃ solution. Compound was recrystallised

from ethanol. M.p. 206°. Yield 20g. (85%). The melting point was in agreement with that reported by James Walker⁹ ;

Fig: (I) to (V):

- R = H, R₁ = H, R₂ = H.
- R = Me; R₁ = H, R₂ = H.
- R = Cl, R₁ = H, R₂ = H.
- R = Br, R₁ = H, R₂ = H.
- R = I, R₁ = H, R₂ = H.
- R = Cl, R₁ = Cl, R₂ = H.
- R = H, R₁ = Cl, R₂ = Cl.
- R = H, R₁ = Me, R₂ = Cl.
- R = H, R₁ = Me, R₂ = Br.
- R = H, R₁ = Me, R₂ = F.

Similarly the other 2-sulfamyl-4-methyl-, 4-sulfamyl-3-methyl-, 4-sulfamyl-2-methyl-, 3-sulfamyl-4-methoxyphenylthioureas were prepared from respective amines : 2-amino-5-methyl-, 4-methyl-6-amino-, 3-methyl-4-amino-, 3-amino-6-methoxy benzene sulfonamides. The melting points, percentage yields and elemental analysis are given in Table 1.

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TABLE 1—SULFAMYL SUBSTITUTED PHENYL THIOUREAS.

Phenyl thiourea	M.P. °C	Yield %	Elemental analysis				
			Calcd		Found		
			C%	H%	C%	H%	H%
4-sulfamyl	206	85	36.36	3.89	36.51	4.10	
2-sulfamyl-4-methyl	205	75	39.18	4.48	39.26	4.67	
3-methyl-4-sulfamyl	220	85	39.18	4.48	39.26	4.58	
2-methyl-4-sulfamyl	193	76	39.18	4.48	39.40	4.52	
3-sulfamyl-4-methoxy	213	50	36.78	4.21	36.93	4.34	

The sulfamyl substituted phenylthiourea showed absorption due to -NH group. The -NH asymmetric stretching frequencies of these compounds lie in the range of 3200-3450 cm^{-1} with higher intensity. The -NH symmetric stretching frequencies show in the range of 3080-3200 cm^{-1} . The -SO₂NH₂ group showed absorption in the range of 1335 to 1370 cm^{-1} and 1145 to 1180 cm^{-1} due to asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibration of S=O respectively.

2. General procedure for the synthesis of (2-sulfamyl substituted anilino)-4-(substituted phenyl) thiazoles.

Sulfamyl substituted phenyl thiourea (0.01 mol) was dissolved in hot water and treated with (0.01 mol) of 2-

chloro acetophenones in the presence of alcohol. The reaction mixture was left on the water bath for 2 hr. On cooling a solid separated. The remainder of the product was precipitated as micro-crystalline solid by the addition of an excess of sodium bicarbonate solution. All the compounds were recrystallised from alcohol.

By following above procedure other sulfamyl substituted phenyl thioureas were condensed with differently substituted 2-chloro acetophenones. The melting points, percentage yields and elemental analysis are given in the Tables 2 to 6.

TABLE 2—2-(4'-SULFAMYL ANILINO)-4-(SUBSTITUTED PHENYL) THIAZOLES : (I)

Phenyl substituent at-4-position	M.P. °C	Yield %	Elemental analysis				
			Calcd		Found		
			C%	H%	C%	H%	H%
R, R ₁ , R ₂ =H	240	75	54.39	3.93	54.65	4.21	
R=Me, R ₁ , R ₂ =H	251*	78	55.65	4.35	55.68	4.45	
R=Cl, R ₁ , R ₂ =H	240	78	49.25	3.28	50.05	3.85	
R=Br, R ₁ , R ₂ =H	255	76	43.90	2.92	43.87	2.90	
R=I, R ₁ , R ₂ =H	226	81	39.40	3.85	40.05	2.63	
R, R ₁ =Cl, R ₂ =H	230	87	44.88	2.99	45.21	3.25	
R=H, R ₁ , R ₂ =Cl	199	87	44.88	2.99	45.20	3.15	
R=H, R ₁ , Me, R ₂ =Cl	177	90	55.81	4.07	56.01	4.25	
R=H, R ₁ =Me, R ₂ =Br	167	85	46.57	3.65	46.31	3.46	
R=H, R ₁ =Me, R ₂ =F	226	80	52.89	3.85	52.98	3.65	

* Crystallised from AcOH.

TABLE 3—2-(2'-SULFAMYL-4'-METHYL ANILINO)-4-(SUBSTITUTED PHENYL) THIAZOLES : (II)

Phenyl Substituent at-4-position	M.P. °C	Yield %	Elemental analysis				
			Calcd		Found		
			C%	H%	C%	H%	H%
R,R ₁ ,R ₂ =H	213	78	55.65	4.34	55.72	4.56	
R=Me,R ₁ ,R ₂ =H	238*	80	56.82	4.73	56.90	4.89	
R=Cl,R ₁ ,R ₂ =H	240	80	50.59	3.68	50.73	3.86	
R=Br,R ₁ ,R ₂ =H	265	76	45.28	3.30	45.18	3.43	
R=I,R ₁ ,R ₂ =H	257*	74	40.76	2.97	40.86	3.03	
R,R ₁ =Cl,R ₂ =H	236	80	46.37	3.14	46.80	3.39	
R=H,R ₁ ,R ₂ =Cl	190	80	46.37	3.14	46.80	3.39	
R=H,R ₁ =Me, R ₂ =Cl	194	81	51.84	4.07	56.01	4.25	
R=H,R ₁ =Me, R ₂ =Br	177	84	46.57	3.65	46.83	3.76	
R=H,R ₁ =Me, R ₂ =F	216	80	54.11	4.24	54.50	4.40	

TABLE 4—2-(3'-METHYL-4'-SULFAMYL ANILINO)-4-(SUBSTITUTED PHENYL) THIAZOLES : (III)

Phenyl Substituent at-4-position	M.P. °C	Yield %	Elemental analysis			
			Calcd		Found	
			C%	H%	C%	H%
R=H,R ₁ ,R ₂ =H	180	76	55.65	4.34	55.71	4.39
R=Me,R ₁ ,R ₂ =H	164	89	56.82	4.73	56.93	4.87
R=Cl,R ₁ ,R ₂ =H	150	76	50.59	3.68	50.65	3.76
R=Br,R ₁ ,R ₂ =H	215	85	45.28	3.30	45.51	3.67
R=I,R ₁ ,R ₂ =H	145	75	40.76	2.97	40.89	3.26
R=R ₁ =Cl,R ₂ =H	249	84	46.37	3.14	46.54	3.54
R=H,R ₁ ,R ₂ =Cl	207	85	46.37	3.14	46.30	3.43
R=H,R ₁ =Me, R ₂ =Cl	215	90	51.84	4.07	51.86	4.10
R=H,R ₁ =Me R ₂ =Br	204	85	46.57	3.65	46.42	3.85
R=H,R ₁ =Me, R ₂ =F	173	80	54.11	4.24	54.31	4.30

TABLE 5—2-(2'-METHYL-4'-SULFAMYL ANILINO)-4-(SUBSTITUTED PHENYL) THIAZOLES : (IV)

Phenyl substituent at-4-position	M.P. °C	Yield %	Elemental analysis			
			Calcd		Found	
			C%	H%	C%	H%
R,R ₁ ,R ₂ =H	196	80	55.65	4.34	55.90	4.70
R=Me,R ₁ ,R ₂ =H	225	76	56.82	4.73	56.89	4.48
R=Cl,R ₁ ,R ₂ =H	245	78	50.59	3.68	50.29	3.72
R=Br,R ₁ ,R ₂ =H	235	81	45.28	3.30	45.43	3.09
R=I,R ₁ ,R ₂ =H	195	75	40.76	2.97	40.74	2.92
R,R ₁ =Cl,R ₂ =H	248	85	46.37	3.14	46.50	3.36
R=H,R ₁ ,R ₂ =Cl	237	84	46.37	3.14	46.61	3.43
R=H,R ₁ =Me,R ₂ =Cl	202	85	51.84	4.07	51.86	4.10
R=H,R ₁ =Me,R ₂ =Cl	174	85	46.57	3.65	46.50	3.40
R=H,R ₁ =Me,R ₂ =F	157	80	54.11	4.24	54.41	4.37

TABLE 6—2-(3'-SULFAMYL-4'-METHOXY ANILINO)-4-(SUBSTITUTED PHENYL) THIAZOLES : (V)

Phenyl substituent at-4-position	M.P. °C	Yield %	Elemental analysis			
			Calcd		Found	
			C%	H%	C%	H%
R,R ₁ ,R ₂ =H	233	85	53.18	4.15	53.26	4.34
R=Me,R ₁ ,R ₂ =H	242*	85	54.40	4.53	54.71	4.69
R=Cl,R ₁ ,R ₂ =H	254	81	48.54	3.53	48.59	3.76
R=Br,R ₁ ,R ₂ =H	267	76	43.63	3.18	43.49	3.48
R=I,R ₁ ,R ₂ =H	238	73	39.42	2.87	39.72	3.10
R,R ₁ =Cl,R ₂ =H	252*	80	44.65	3.02	44.80	3.37
R=H,R ₁ ,R ₂ =Cl	240	80	44.65	3.02	44.76	3.41
R=H,R ₁ =Me,R ₂ =Cl	194	85	49.81	3.90	45.06	4.12
R=H,R ₁ =Me,R ₂ =Br	187	85	44.83	3.73	45.24	4.12
R=H,R ₁ =Me,R ₂ =F	225*	80	51.90	4.07	52.33	4.42

*Crystallised from AcOH.

The IR spectra showed absorption due to imino (-NH-) group and (-SO₂NH₂) group and due to thiazole nucleus : The -NH stretching frequencies of these compounds lie in the range of 3320 to 3500 cm⁻¹ with higher intensity. The -NH bending frequencies show absorption in the range of 1600 to 1640 cm⁻¹. All the compounds show absorption due to asymmetric stretching of S=O (1370, 1330 cm⁻¹) and symmetric stretching of S=O (1180, 1160cm⁻¹) groups. The absorption due to thiazole nucleus showed band around 1570, 1440, 1365, 1020, 815 cm⁻¹.

Activity : The 2-(sulfamyl substitutedanilino)-4-(substituted phenyl) thiazoles, selecting few of compounds from each series were tested for the antibacterial activity, against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. typhi*, and *S. comma* and found to be inactive.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. D. D. Khanolkar, Head of Department, for providing facilities during this work. Thanks are due to Director, Haffkine Institute, Bombay, for testing antibacterial activities. One of the authors (MSS) is grateful to Marathwada University for the award of a research fellowship.

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